

METHODOLOGY OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF ARTS TEACHERS

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Abstract. *The article provides for the improvement of the methods of professional training of future teachers of fine and applied arts, the development of mechanisms for the development of artistic and technical skills.*

Keywords: *global, institutions, systems, applied arts, creativity, vocational training, technical training, pedagogical technologies.*

As the President of our country said, "Science, education and training are the cornerstone of development and the force that makes the country powerful and the nation great."

The requirements of the current globalization show that highly qualified, competitive creative specialists, especially future pedagogues, working in conditions of accelerated development of science and pedagogical technologies one of the important factors of training is to improve the quality of educational creative training of future visual arts teachers studying in the higher education system.

In the current period of development of our society, it is important to train qualified specialists who can withstand the competition of the market economy. After all, the importance of the expert personnel factor in the development of society is a fact of life that does not require proof. In recent years, large-scale work has been done and is being done on the training of specialist personnel, improving their professional quality and efficiency. In particular, special attention is being paid to developing qualities such as independence, creativity, entrepreneurship, and activity of trained specialists.

There are a number of inconsistencies and contradictions in the training of highly qualified artist teachers, including: - scientific methodical training of graduates of higher educational institutions - future teachers of fine arts in accordance with the requirements for the professional training of current artist-teachers inadequacy of the content; - low quality and effectiveness of students' scientific theoretical and methodical training (knowledge and skills, visual art literacy) in the higher education system; - in the system of scientific theoretical and methodical training of future artists-teachers, their that it is not considered as a factor of professional formation; - their low level of practical training in the educational process, etc. Also, the inconsistency between the objective necessity of forming the skills of educational activity in students and the state of educational activity in various theoretical and practical trainings according to the content, methods and results of learners is visible. This means considering the scientific and practical principles of methodological preparation of students for future professional activities. At the same time, it should be noted that in the pedagogical literature, higher school students are characterized not only by studying in the auditorium, but also by their independent education. Therefore, future fine and applied art in the higher education system means to activate the theoretical and practical-creative training of teachers. Creative preparation of students is the main indicator of their professional ability and is formed on the basis of continuous artistic education. After all, "continuous education

creates a necessary condition for the formation of a creative, socially active, spiritually mature person, training of highly qualified competitive personnel."

Practical and theoretical training in all types of art is the first step in the preparation of future specialists in the perfect mastery of depicting existence in real images. In order to accurately and skillfully depict the original form of objects on paper, the student must master fine art knowledge and apply it in practice - learn to draw based on nature, memory and imagination. . Of course, in order to perform such creative tasks, it is important for a person to have certain abilities and to be able to work on himself continuously and independently.

Although fine art can be recognized as a factor in improving the educational process in the subject, it is directly related to the didactic effect of improving the quality and effectiveness of fine art education in general secondary schools. no special studies have been carried out to investigate its possibilities. In fact, improving the quality and efficiency of visual art education in school education is important not only for the art education system, but also for the personnel training system as a whole, that is, the formation of elements of visual literacy in students is crucial to the future specialist's profession. nazar forms the skills to approach one's professional activity with creativity. After all, the skills acquired in fine art classes are the specific parameters of objects - their shape, structural structure, color, material, texture, proportions, economy, and most importantly, the laws of aesthetic parameters and their proportionality - theoretical knowledge and practical skills, mainly visual art. Content is added in horse lessons.

Perfect teaching of the practical aspects of painting, drawing and composition included in the block of compulsory subjects and the modern teaching of all subjects included in the curriculum for their professional training to the future teachers of fine arts at the higher educational institution. development and implementation of technologies plays an important role in the thorough preparation of the holders of these professions for professional and pedagogical activities.

Methodology and individual system of teaching drawing of each pedagogue in any case, if the student has the right technical training, he will grow up and develop as a successful artist in the future, regardless of whether he takes lessons under the guidance of any pedagogue-artist. However, the skill of a pedagogue is defined in the fact that he can give instructions to each student in accordance with his imaging technique, widely use educational methods and give correct instructions to the student. The skill of drawing is the ability of a person to be able to make a certain form truthfully by using certain methods and techniques based on previous experience. Skill in artistic creative activity is created on the basis of previously acquired knowledge and skills. No matter what profession a person has, if he approaches his work and training diligently and lovingly, he will perfectly master its secrets, at the same time, he will realize himself and find perfection in this field.

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